

ILLUMINATION OF PROFESSION CHOICE ISSUES IN YOUNG PEOPLE IN DAVANI'S WORKS

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Abstract. The article analyzes the opinions of Eastern scholars on the issues of directing young people to professions in Davani's works. In particular, it is pointed out by the scholar that their age characteristics, interests, needs, and aspirations are important in directing young people to the profession.

Key words: personality, career choice, career guidance, vocational training, world of professions, interest, passion, work, mastering a profession.

Аннотация. В статье проведен анализ взглядов на вопросы профессиональной реабилитации молодежи в работах Давани из восточного алломаса. Особенно в аллома показано, что при выборе профессии молодыми людьми важны их возрастные особенности, интересы, потребности, уровень устремлений.

Ключевые слова: личность, выбор профессии, профориентация, профподготовка, мир профессий, интерес, увлечение, труд, занятие профессией.

Аннотация. Мақолада Шарқ алломаларидан Давоний асарларида ёшларни касб-хунарга йўнатириш масалаларига доир фикрларини таҳлили амалга оширилган. Айниқса, аллома томонидан ёшларни касбга йўналтиришда уларнинг ёш хусусиятлари, қизиқиш, эҳтиёж, интилишлар даражаси муҳим эканлиги кўрсатиб ўтилади.

Калит сўзлар: шахс, касб танлаш, касбга йўналтириш, касб-хунарга ўргатиш, касблар олами, қизиқиш, иштиёқ, меҳнат, хунар эгаллаш.

In the East, providing education and training to young people and teaching them a trade is one of the ancient traditions. Especially the artisans and craftsmen, architects and painters, farmers and herdsmen, who attached great importance to learning the secrets of their trades in raising their children or apprentices. It is worth noting that various stories and proverbs have been collected over the centuries, showing that our people pay so much attention to the education of the young generation. For example, there are many wise sayings such as "A disciple who does not follow the teacher is not a disciple", "A skilled person is not despised" or "Seventy skills are not enough for a young man" It is a clear proof that they have encouraged them to become business owners.

In the teachings of Eastern thinkers, the idea of training boys and girls in a profession, along with education and upbringing, occupies an important place. It can be seen that the issues of career choice and career guidance are not new for today, but are being studied as an age-old problem. Davani, one of the encyclopedic scholars of the East, also expressed noteworthy opinions about children's occupation. The teacher should know very well the skills of the students in which profession they are interested. If the child is engaged in a certain profession or science, it is necessary to support him in every way and create the necessary conditions for acquiring this science or profession. Every person, writes Davani, does not have the ability to master all professions, but a certain person has the ability for a profession [2].

Those who seek to learn a profession will focus all their talents on mastering that profession, and as a result, they will quickly and thoroughly master the professions they love. These thoughts of Davani are very similar to the following thoughts of Farabi: "People who voluntarily strive to acquire a profession and achieve perfection are the owners of true virtue and true artists". If a person does not have passion for a certain profession, he should never be forced to take up this profession, otherwise he can only torture himself [1].

Davani divides professions that benefit a person into three, that is, they depend on a person's spiritual (spiritual) power, and the first one is related to the human mind, which includes the ministry profession. The second comes as a result of education. This includes the study of astronomy, mathematics, medicine and geometry. The third is professions that show a person's courage and bravery: these are fighting against the enemy, guarding the border, etc.

A master scientist criticizes people who do not want to do a job or a profession. Like Jami, he condemns young people who do not take up a profession because of their father's wealth. He calls the young people to work and acquire a profession, according to him, a person can achieve perfection and happiness only in work.

Thus, Davani believed that mastering a profession is one of the most beautiful qualities of a person. A person who strives to acquire a profession and improve it will also benefit society, so such a person is worthy of all praise [3].

He divides people into categories based primarily on their profession. The first category includes scientists, viceroys, astrologers, judges, engineers, Muslim jurists; the military to the second category; and the third category includes merchants, artisans and others. The fourth category consists of peasants and agricultural workers.

Davani especially glorifies the farming profession. Like Alisher Navoi, Davani highly values the work of farmers, because farmers are the people who provide food and material wealth to people of all classes. Without their zeal, the human race would disappear like petty traders, because other classes of people cannot create enough to live on, but give what they create to someone else, take it from one place to another, or change its form.

One of Davani's positive views on the profession is that he sings first of all the work of the common people, especially the work of the farmer, who proved that a person can become a well-rounded person by achieving happiness only through his honest work. Therefore, he calls to always respect and appreciate the work of professionals. Davani also expressed valuable ideas about the development of children's mental abilities and training for professions.

Davani talks about the need for the teacher to know the profession that the children are interested in and their abilities. Of course, not all professions can be mastered, but every person has a talent for a profession, says the scientist. A person who aspires to acquire a profession will spend all his talents and quickly learn this profession. The great thinker Farobi also emphasized such an idea [1].

If this or that person does not have passion for a certain profession, he cannot be forced, otherwise he will suffer and this profession will not bring him happiness, he says. Davani divides professions that are beneficial to a person into three: he shows that it is related to the spiritual power of people, he shows the first one as belonging to the human mind, and he includes the ministerial profession.

The second one is formed as a result of education, including astronomy, mathematics, medicine, and geometry. The third includes professions related to the courage and bravery of people, that is, fighting against the enemy, guarding the border, and others. A scientist is very critical of people who do not have a profession. He condemns young people who do not take up a profession, believing in their father's wealth. While working promotes mastery, it believes that work is the source of human perfection and happiness.

Davani's views on profession are important because he glorifies the work of ordinary people, the work of peasants. It proves that a person can achieve happiness only because of his work, and that work is a criterion for the perfection of a person as a person [1].

In conclusion, it should be noted that studying the ideas on choosing a profession, orientation to a profession in the works of Eastern scholars, applying them to practical life, will help the growing young generation to choose a conscious

profession. And this is one of the main tasks of the society to train children in professions from a young age. It also serves to enrich their professional understanding, imagination and knowledge.

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